

Discovery Multimedia in The Wake of Covid-19 Pandemic

*Farhah Nor Azam, Nur Athirah Md Ariffin,
Nur Nabhilah Mohd Zaki, Fadhilnor Rahmad

Faculty of Information Management
Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM)
Selangor, Malaysia

*Email: farhah501@gmail.com

Received Date: 20 August 2021
Accepted Date: 4 September 2021
Published Date: 10 September 2021

Abstract. World Health Organization identified the Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) as a rare pneumonia disease that originated in Wuhan, on January 12, 2020, before it became an outbreak in all countries. As a result, the multimedia has become a crucial platform for disseminating critical information about the global epidemic. Multimedia can be described as information represented, stored, communicated, and processed digitally through the integration of media such as text, graphics, animation, video, and audio through computer control. This article is about discovery multimedia in the wake of Covid-19 pandemic. Multimedia tools play a significant role in this situation as a response to Covid 19 in any sector. There are various types of Multimedia Applied During Pandemic Covid19 to help convey information accurately to avoid wrong facts. Multimedia also will give many advantages during covid-19 pandemic that we can avoid fake news and will assist you in obtaining accurate information and the material will be updated periodically. Managing information during a pandemic is critical for ensuring that public health remains the government's top priority. Similarly, to keep up with COVID-19 news and prevention initiatives, the general public must be given accurate and timely information.

Keywords: Covid-19 Pandemic, Multimedia Tools, Discovery

Introduction

Coronavirus disease that came originated from Wuhan; China has been fast spreading in more than 213 countries. The covid 19 pandemic has affected 1,524,162 people that are confirmed positive and 92,941 death cases since 10 April 2020. It transmitted through either direct or indirect contact between infection person when they speak, breathe, cough and sneeze. In the same way, Malaysia also was reported

three waves of covid 19 from 31 March 2020 until now and this virus cause increasingly per day number patient of covid 19 that warded in Intensive Care Unit (ICU) (Ain et al., 2020). During the outbreak situation across the world, the World Health Organization (WHO) has implemented several Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) to public such as, avoid 3Cs which stand for crowded places, close-contact settings and confined spaces and practice 3W that is wash hand frequently, wear masks and warn stay at home (World Health Organization, 2020). According to this, many sectors and industries had to deal with the standardize policies and procedures from government to prevent the virus became spread widely.

On top of that, our engineers and researchers in various field have cooperate together in developed technology for managed this global emergency situation. They were focused on multimedia tools, method and applications (Chen, 2021). To illustrate, multimedia is defined as the information that represented, stored, transmitted and processed digitally through computer control integration of media such as text, graphic, animation, video and audio (Costello, 2017). It is necessary to understand the term of multimedia in order to find out the relationship between multimedia toward covid 19. Last but not least, the term paper will be discussed on the title of Discovery Multimedia in The Wake of Covid 19 Pandemic by specific looking deeply into three divided section which is role of multimedia during Covid-19 pandemic, types of multimedia that implemented during Covid-19 pandemic and advantages using multimedia during Covid-19 pandemic.

Roles of Multimedia During Covid-19 Pandemic

Based on the research done by Shu-Ching Chen (2021), the SARS-CoV-2 is very tough to control and prevent from the society and cause many policies to follows like lockdowns, quarantine and mask orders. In this situation, multimedia tools show a significant role as a response toward covid 19 in any industry. First of all, we can see the role of multimedia during covid 19 pandemic is a tool for online distance learning (ODL). The development of information and communication technology bring a great implication within the education system in Malaysia. In addition, the pandemic has pushed out the educational institutions across the globe to change teaching and learning method to online medium. Apart from this, there has been increasing trend in using multimedia among student, teachers and lecturers from kindergarten, primary school, secondary school, polytechnic even university also for the purpose of online learning such as Microsoft and Google Meet application (Baharuddin et al., 2020). The different application is serves different quality of multimedia based on the objectives (Debajyoti et al., 2020). In consequence, although they had to online distance learning session from home but this can indirectly improve students' skills in using information and communication technology (ICT) as well as compete healthily with other students in line with the digitalization era.

Besides that, multimedia act as strengthening the economy and people life. The article received from the portal of MCMC, Malaysia stated that technology and communication are the foundation for the strengthening of the economy and the lives

of the people even in the current difficult situation. On the same point, this is the main commitment by government to reduce and closing gaps of digital between society for empowering their economy. So, that the community have stay connected and get benefit from high quality connectivity (Baharuddin et al., 2021). For instance, the use of broadband and implementation of 5G in every country especially Malaysia assistance the public to receive the benefits for a better life. This can be seen from the total number of users and payments broadband in 2019 up to 10 percent which is 2.95 million compared during 2018. To add, the development of ICT is driven by many factors such as better coverage, abilities and increasing of data usage and smartphones (Malaysian Communication Multimedia Commission, 2020). Therefore, the emergence of e-commerce and electronic services nowadays especially in movement control order (MCO) has become the top choices for consumers to purchase their needs. Thus, we can see the advancement of technology plays a role as an industry intrinsically and help manage all the economic activities. Such as increase revenue to the Small Medium Enterprise (SME) (Ahlam, 2016).

Moreover, Communication Forum written by Ahlam Binti Abdul Aziz, 2016 shows the improvement of technology as a role and gives contributions toward communication development in organization. He spoke that communication technology not anymore for ease interaction between staff in organization but also has been streamlined as an intermediary within convey information toward stakeholders and shareholders while helping to simplify task and order in the organization such as email. On the other hand, multimedia also makes it easier for employees since they work from home (WFH) due to the outbreak. Some of organization are taking advantages to use the multimedia platform for positive side towards their company such as hiring workers through online website, Webex, Skype and Zoom. The uses of multimedia during covid 19 give benefit for organization to save time, reduce non-expenditure cost and stabilize their operational and financial position. Furthermore, a lot of telecommunication mediums are applied by corporate government in order to spread information to the society as main interest for decide and determine the effectiveness of new normal practices. In the same way, social advocacy campaign and media strategic action also support government to implement the positive living value towards public (Malaysian Communication Multimedia Commission, 2020). Last, but not least, globalization and digitalization has changed the style of organizing whether corporate organization or non-corporate organization and compete in the market sector (Modimogale & Kroeze, 2011).

Types of Multimedia That Implemented During Covid-19 Pandemic

The COVID-19 health crisis has posed new problems for the transmission of accurate health information throughout the world. In dealing with the COVID-19 virus, disinformation propagated across multiple social media platforms makes it more difficult to communicate accurate and reliable information to the public.

Everyone needs to play role in order for the country to tackle this significant problem that affects the lives. The need for accurate information about the covid-19 pandemic is critical for disease prevention.

Media, newspapers and social media have become the public's reliance on information on COVID-19 since the MCO's torture in Malaysia. All information on COVID-19 is always published on television, press conference and various information channels including internet media platforms and social media. By sharing the news and update information might help to keep the public alert with this virus. This information is presented in both government and private media.

The Ministry of Health (MOH) and the Majlis Keselamatan Negara (MKN) are responsible for sharing information and control on COVID-19 with the public. This is to ensure that the public obtain authentic information. To ensure the clarity, integrity, and consistency of information, the MOH and NSC choose credible spokesmen to deliver COVID-19 updates. The importance of media in delivering information to the public during the MCO has also been emphasized and encouraging people to stay at home, take a vaccine, exercise excellent personal hygiene and maintain social distance when in public areas such as at supermarket or when buying a grocery thing.

The Ministry of Health (MoH) has also made an effort and be transparent in its response to the pandemic by giving enough and up-to-date information to the public through three major platforms which are the Official Portal of the Ministry of Health, Facebook page called the Crisis Preparedness and Response Centre (CRPC), Kementerian Kesihatan Malaysia (KKM), and the KKM Telegram (My Government, 2020). In addition, The Ministry has provided awareness programs on basic protective and hygiene measures to minimize transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in simple infographic form to reach the public easily. This involves hand-washing practices, as well as the use of hand sanitizers and face masks. Furthermore, many infographics related to COVID-19 have been created and uploaded to the website to encourage public involvement and assure public access to accurate information.

Besides the government, the media, celebrities, and other influencers have also urged people to stay at home and avoid mass gatherings. The hashtag #stayhome has been widely utilized in the media and it is hoped that vital information about COVID-19 can reach people at all levels of society. Malaysians basically relied on television for current COVID-19 information during the MCO, followed by online news sources. In particular, young people preferred referring to the social media such as MOH Twitter and Instagram account for information related with COVID-19 news.

On MoH's Twitter and Facebook accounts, they are always informing the daily cases of covid-19 as information and awareness. In the form of posters or infographics, total daily cases, case breakdown by location, number of patients requiring oxygen, number of deaths and number of recovered patients are displayed. Furthermore, as a precaution, the list of newly detected covid clusters is shared with the public. Clearly, they do not hide any information regarding COVID-19 case data that occurs in Malaysia. During the covid outbreak, they not only shared daily cases but also carried out their obligations by raising awareness about personal care and health. Taking vaccines for each individual is also their main focus. The MOH and local media have also released an animated short video titled 'MakCik Kiah Family &

COVID-19' that explains how the COVID-19 virus spreads on social media and on television. The objective of the video is to raise public awareness so that people are alert about the virus, which can have devastating consequences if it is infected.

Aside from the MOH and the media, the World Health Organization (WHO) and the private sector also played a role in curbing the COVID-19. On the official WHO website, there are live interviews regarding covid19 from all over the world. They also highlighted the effects that will occur to humans if the virus continues to spread. The public's trust in the virus's information dissemination activities is increasing. The simple use of language, complete and easy-to-understand graphics and videos about COVID-19 are very helpful.

During times of public health crisis, public health information has been effectively transmitted via television, providing the public with much-needed knowledge for disease prevention and control while also improving public confidence in the government's ability to manage the epidemic.

Advantages of Using Multimedia During Covid-19 Pandemic

The use of a computer to show and mix text, images, music, and video with links and tools that allow the user to explore, engage, create, and communicate is known as multimedia. This concept includes four components that are fundamental to multimedia. This review outlines the advantages of multimedia during coronavirus pandemic on health-care professionals and on the general population. However, if used wisely and prudently, multimedia serves as a powerful tool for changing people's behavior and to promote the well-being of individual and public health.

The advantage of multimedia is to avoid misinformation, stigma, and fake news. The spread of false information is a major issue with current online media. The spread of misinformation about SARS-CoV-2 has been no different, with claims that the virus was created in a lab as a bioterrorism agent or that the symptoms are induced by the 5G mobile network. Avoiding stigma has also been a concern in the multimedia era. Many sites referred to the virus as the "Wuhan virus" or something similar early in the COVID-19 outbreak, before the disease or virus were given formal names, with the hashtag "Wuhan virus" trending on Twitter. Unfortunately, this phrase has the effect of stigmatizing residents of that city, as well as associating them with people of a particular ethnic group. Unfortunately, this phrase has a propensity to stigmatize residents of that city and to associate them with people of a particular ethnicity, inciting fear, and xenophobia in some circumstances.

However, it is critical that credible media outlets not only ignore but also strive to correct falsehoods. This can be accomplished by considering who their audience might trust, enlisting trustworthy experts, demonstrating empathy for people affected, employing appropriate language, and clearly and carefully defining terminology, such as what a "community case" means. The WHO's 'myth buster' section, for example, debunks several common misconceptions concerning COVID-19.

Appropriate language in multimedia is important in countering stigma particularly with reference to places or countries. The virus does not discriminate based on nationality or other factors, there is no reason for journalists to do so. Furthermore, nomenclature like as "patient zero" and "super spreaders" have been questioned, with substantial criticism levelled when the name of the first British case of COVID-19 was revealed in the UK media. To minimize stigma and its potentially disastrous consequences, reporting should focus on the big picture rather than details.

In addition to reporting the event, multimedia can provide audiences with useful information or 'news you can use' such as local phone numbers for healthcare services or handwashing instructions. These tiny, practical initiatives from reliable and up-to-date sources could assist the public learn about guidance from larger governing organizations that they might not otherwise hear.

Besides that, multimedia can be a moving fact. It has been roughly 1 year and a half since the COVID-19 outbreak was first reported, and the difference between what we knew about the virus when it first appeared and what we know today, including its clinical development and at-risk demographics, is simply amazing. Everyone will have access to accurate and clear information through multimedia.

Multimedia will assist you in getting accurate information because the material will be updated on a regular basis (Baharuddin et al., 2019a). For example, by the next morning a news story you read one day could be completely out-of-date, and this has resulted in a slew of queries from the public about the spread and the virus. Furthermore, as new evidence has become available in recent weeks, experts and public health officials have altered their opinions, advice, and recommendations accordingly, and it has been stated that these modifications have made it difficult to create confidence. So, multimedia will aid in overcoming the problem of inaccurate information continuing to proliferate and be read.

Conclusion

Managing information during this outbreak plays a very important role to the public especially frontliners to always be prepared for the increasing of patients in the hospital. The government also can plan strategies to ensure the stability of the country and the health of the people are in a safe place. The people must stay be provided with accurate and timely information in order to keep up with COVID-19 news. The government and related agencies must be ready to react swiftly when new scientific discoveries are made and new information becomes available. This is especially important in light of the spread of disinformation, fake news, and conspiracy theories regarding covid-19 across the world. It is necessary to update outdated information and replaced it with latest information, erroneous facts must be rectified and public announcements and instructions must be promptly disseminated.

Today's technological advances show that many sectors are concerned with the use of multimedia. Everyone has to run with multimedia things. It is because multimedia is very important for our daily life. When having multimedia, the use of video, images, voice can help to communicate information to the public more easily. People

are also able to get information more quickly. In addition, the right tools and channels are key determinants for ensuring effective public health information delivery. The ability of health authorities to understand and apply these technologies is critical in instilling trust in the intended population.

References

Ain U. M. S, Syafiqah N. A. S, Rathedevi T, Nor K. N, Azmawani A. R, Zamberi S, Aini I, Mohamed T. H. S, (2020). Covid-19 Outbreak in Malaysia: Actions Taken by The Malaysian Government. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 97, (pp. 108-116). Retrieved June 6, 2021 from www.elsevier.com/locate/ijid

Ahlan. A. A, (2016). Peranan Teknologi Komunikasi dan Sumbangannya ke arah Perkembangan Komunikasi dalam Organisasi yang Berkesan. Retrieved June 6, 2021 from *Forum komunikasi*. Vol. 11, No. 2, (pp. 51-64).

Baharuddin, M. F., Masrek, M. N., & Shuhidan, S. M. (2019a). Innovative Work Behaviour of School Teachers: a Conceptual Framework. *IJAEDU- International E-Journal of Advances in Education*, 5(14), 213–221. <https://doi.org/10.18768/ijaedu.593851>

Baharuddin, M. F., Masrek, M. N., & Shuhidan, S. M. (2020). Content validity of assessment instrument for innovative work behaviour of Malaysian school teachers. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(4), 1940–1946.

Baharuddin, M. F., Masrek, M. N., Shuhidan, S. M., Razali, M. H., & Rahman, M. S. (2021). Evaluating the Content Validity of Digital Literacy Instrument for School Teachers in Malaysia through Expert Judgement. *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering*, 11(07), 71–78. <https://doi.org/10.46338/ijetae0721>

Costello, Vic. (2017). *Multimedia Foundations Core Concepts for Digital Design*. Second Edition. New York, NY: Routledge, 2017. Retrieved June 6, 2021 from <https://books.google.com.my/>

Debajyoti Pal, V. V, S. P, (July 1, 2020). Online Learning during Covid-19: Students' Perception of Multimedia Quality. Retrieved June 6, 2021 from IAIT 2020: Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Advances in Information Technology (pp. 1-6). ACM Digital Library.

Emma Mohanad, Jen Sern Tham, Suffian Hadi Ayub, Rezal Hamzah, Hasrul Hashim & Arina Anis Azlan. (2020, November 22). Relationship Between COVID-19 Information Sources and Attitudes in Battling the Pandemic Among the Malaysian Public: Cross- Sectional Survey Study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22, Article 11, Retrieved June 8, 2021 from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7674144/>

Discovery Multimedia in The Wake of Covid-19 Pandemic

Modimogale, L., & Kroeze, J.H. (2011). The Role Of ICT Within Small And Medium Enterprises In Gauteng. Retrieved June 6, 2021 from Communication of the IBIMA.

Official Portal of Malaysian Communication Multimedia Commission, (May 17, 2020). Powerful Communication Technology Society Facing Crisis Covid-19. Retrieved June 6, 2021 from <https://www.mcmc.gov.my/>

Official Portal of World Health Organization, (December 13, 2020). Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19): How is it transmitted?. Retrieved June 6, 2021 from <https://www.who.int/news-room/q-a-detail/coronavirus-disease-covid-19-how-is-it-transmitted#>

S. -C. Chen, (2021). Multimedia Research for Response and Management of Covid-19 and Future Pandemics. Retrieved June 6, 2021 from Journals & Magazines. IEEE Multimedia. Vol. 28, No. 1, (pp. 5-6), Jan.- March 2021, doi: 10. 1109/MMUL.2021.3063011